

AI Depression Detection in Adolescent and Young Adult During the Time of Pandemic

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Abstract— Depression rates increase dramatically during the middle and high school years with prevalence rates for adolescents at 7.5% [1]. During the COVID-19 pandemic, depression rates increased by over 60% [2]. Evidence shows that young adults are most vulnerable to the mental health effects of the pandemic. Compared to children in higher-income households, those in lower-income households more often received a diagnosis of mental, behavioral, and developmental disorders (22.1% versus 13.9%), and less often seen a health care provider in the previous year (80.4% versus 93.8%) [3]. The delayed detection and intervention process leads to the drop of the recover rates.

Our goal is to develop an AI system to screen depression earlier on at low or no cost. We target early onsite emotional symptoms before they progress to neurovegetative and neurocognitive symptoms, according to the mental disorder symptoms taxonomy. The number one impacting factor to AI solutions is the quality of the dataset. For this reason, we researched the depression symptoms and current clinical detection approaches in order to define the scope of our dataset.

For our AI solution, we analyzed the performance of non-verbal emotional expressions and natural language sentiment features in face videos and contextual content from survey results, public datasets, and social media content. We utilized Convolutional Neural Network to conduct multi-class classification on non-verbal cues, yielding 83% accuracy rate when epoch set to 80, applied Bag-of-Words and Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency on text vectorization, logistic regression on natural language features, and sentiment analysis on twitter data. We concluded that there is a large correlation between emotional signals discovered by AI tools and depression symptoms. Therefore, AI tools can play a big role in detecting emotional symptoms of depression. It can be used as an early screen outreach tool to raise awareness in young adults and reveal complementary cues in clinical depression practices.

Keywords— mental health, disorder, depression, pandemic, young adult, convolutional neural network, logistic regression, bag-of-words, TF-IDF, twitter, sentiment analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Depression (a mental health disorder) is characterized by persistently depressed mood or loss of interest in activities, causing significant impairment in daily life including disruption in education, work, relationships, and roles people play in society. According to the World Health Organization, depression is the leading cause of disability worldwide, affecting an estimated 350 million people [4].

Depression onset increases dramatically during the middle and high school years, with nationally representative prevalence rates for adolescents estimated at 7.5% [1]. “At its worst, depression can lead to suicide. Close to 800,000 people die due to suicide every year. Suicide is the second leading cause of death in 15-29-year-olds.” [4]

During the COVID-19 pandemic, depression rates increased by over 60% comparing the national survey data in mid-July, 2020 and the data in 2019 conducted by the U.S. Census Bureau [5]. The evidence shows that young adults are most vulnerable to the mental health

impacts of the pandemic. This observation in the US is broadly comparable to that observed in studies of young adults in China and Switzerland [2]. In addition, the social-media-based emotional support slightly increases the odds of depression for the young adults compared to the face-to-face emotional support [6]. The timely diagnosis of depression becomes an utmost necessity globally.

This paper will discuss AI based solution proposals for early depression detection. One of the benefits of this proposal is that it can be accessible at low or no cost to low income families who may have less access to health care providers. Compared to children in higher-income households, those in lower-income households more often received a diagnosis of an mental, behavioral, and developmental disorders (MBDDs) (22.1% versus 13.9%), and less often seen a health care provider in the previous year (80.4% versus 93.8%) [3].

Another benefit of our proposal is the early screening rather than waiting for the early symptoms to progress to clinical cases. The delayed detection and intervention process (2–6 years) leads to the drop of the recover rates, approximately 60% at 2 years, 40% at 4 years, and 30% at 6 years with comorbid anxiety having a key role in limiting recovery [7].

II. TECHNOLOGIES SELECTION

Kinesics of the face, or facial expressions are part of the essential nonverbal cues.

Machine Learning researchers tend to combine the analysis of visual and contextual information. This combination increases the accuracy of the model compared to when each is analyzed individually. In our solution, we applied AI to both videos and images as well as natural language contents.

Facial emotion recognition models have three main elements: face and facial component detection, feature extraction, and expression classification. The key variations in different recognition techniques lie within feature extraction and the classifier.

Conventional approaches to this problem include several different feature extraction techniques. One such technique involves the use of geometric feature extraction. The classifier then uses the distances and angles between the points to decide which emotion the person is expressing. An example of this type of feature extraction is shown below.

Fig.1 Geometric Feature Extraction [8]

Another conventional facial emotion recognition approach involves the use of appearance feature extraction based on recording various statistics of the pixels' values within the face image [9]. This approach is usually less accurate compared to the others because of the use of global features. It does not account for certain parts of the face not being as important as other parts when determining emotion.

The third approach uses deep learning Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). In the convolution layer, the computer extracts high level features by moving a kernel, called filter, over the entire image and reducing its dimensions. The max pooling layer also reduces the size of the features by extracting the dominant convolved features. Both of these are used to reduce computational power.

Among all above approaches, we chose to build Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) models for supervised learning. CNN is a better fit for recognizing and accurately categorizing image and video input due to CNN's property and architecture design. The CNN is able to downscale inputs, and is very resistant against shifts or distortions in the input. Therefore, it has a short training time.

For natural language processing sentiment analysis, there are broad spectrum of machine learning technologies and libraries. We used Bag-of-Words, TF-IDF, and logistic regression machine learning models.

III. CURRENT STANDARD DEPRESSION DETECTION SURVEY APPROACHES

The number one impacting factor to AI solutions is the quality of the dataset. For this reason, we researched the depression symptoms and current clinical detection approaches in order to define the scope of our dataset.

A. Depression Symptoms

In order to dive into the approaches for diagnosing depression, we first should understand the symptoms.

The symptoms are listed in the following DSM taxonomy.

Fig. 2 Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders [DSM] Taxonomy

The National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH) presents a list of questions that an individual should consider answering if he/she wants to check for depression. All these questions are aimed to surface the symptoms listed above.

B. Self Report and Clinical Screens

We studied three major approaches that are being widely used across populations. Based on this study, we incorporated the core features to collect along with additional multi-media dataset to analyze verbal and non-verbal cues using AI technologies.

CES-D and CESD-R (Revised)

The Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale (CES-D) was created in 1977 by Laurie Radloff, and revised in 2004 by William Eaton and others. CES-D is a screening test measuring symptoms defined by the American Psychiatric Association' Diagnostic and Statistical Manual (DSM-V) for a major

depressive episode [10][11] This is a self report depression scale for research to measure the self-reported symptoms of depression in the past week.

Scale items:
Below is a list of some ways you may have felt or behaved. Please indicate how often you have felt this way during the last week by checking the appropriate space. Please only provide one answer to each question.

During the past week:	Rarely or none of the time (less than 1 day)	Some or a little of the time (1-2 days)	Occasionally or a moderate amount of time (3-4 days)	Most or all of the time (5-7 days)
1. I was bothered by things that usually don't bother me.				
2. I did not feel like eating; my appetite was poor.				
3. I felt that I could not shake off the blues even with help from my family or friends.				
4. I felt I was just as good as other people.				
5. I had trouble keeping my mind on what I was doing.				
6. I felt depressed.				
7. I felt that everything I did was an effort.				
8. I felt hopeful about the future.				
9. I thought my life had been a failure.				
10. I felt fearful.				
11. My sleep was restless.				
12. I was happy.				
13. I talked less than usual.				
14. I felt lonely.				
15. People were unfriendly.				
16. I enjoyed life.				
17. I had crying spells.				
18. I felt sad.				
19. I felt that people disliked me.				
20. I could not get going.				

Scoring:	Rarely (Less than 1 day)	Some (1-2 days)	Occasionally (3-4 days)	Most (5-7 days)
Questions 4, 8, 12, and 16	3	2	1	0
All other questions	0	1	2	3

Fig. 3 Depression Screen Survey, Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression (CES-D) [12]

CESD-R (Revision)

Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale – Revised (CESD-R)

Below is a list of the ways you might have felt or behaved. Please check the boxes to tell me how often you have felt this way in the past week or so.	Last Week				Nearly every day for 2 weeks
	Not at all or Less than 1 day	1 - 2 days	3 - 4 days	5 - 7 days	
My appetite was poor.	0	1	2	3	4
I could not shake off the blues.	0	1	2	3	4
I had trouble keeping my mind on what I was doing.	0	1	2	3	4
I felt depressed.	0	1	2	3	4
My sleep was restless.	0	1	2	3	4
I felt sad.	0	1	2	3	4
I could not get going.	0	1	2	3	4
Nothing made me happy.	0	1	2	3	4
I felt like a bad person.	0	1	2	3	4
I lost interest in my usual activities.	0	1	2	3	4
I slept much more than usual.	0	1	2	3	4
I felt like I was moving too slowly.	0	1	2	3	4
I felt fidgety.	0	1	2	3	4
I wished I were dead.	0	1	2	3	4
I wanted to hurt myself.	0	1	2	3	4
I was tired all the time.	0	1	2	3	4
I did not like myself.	0	1	2	3	4
I lost a lot of weight without trying to.	0	1	2	3	4
I had a lot of trouble getting to sleep.	0	1	2	3	4
I could not focus on the important things.	0	1	2	3	4

REFERENCE: Eaton, W. W., Smith, C., Ybarra, M., Muntaner, C., Tien, A. (2004). Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale: review and revision (CESD and CESD-R). In ME Maruish (Ed.), *The Use of Psychological Testing for Treatment Planning and Outcomes Assessment* (3rd Ed.), Volume 3: Instruments for Adults, pp. 363-377. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.

Fig 4 Revised Depression Screen Survey [13]

Below is an explanation of the algorithm used to calculate the depression scores and categories. "The 20 items in CESD-R scale measure symptoms of depression in nine different groups as defined by the American Psychiatric Association Diagnostic and Statistical Manual, fifth edition. These symptom groups are shown below, with their associated scale question numbers to the right." [10]

- Sadness(Dysphoria):** Question numbers 2,4, 6
- Loss of Interest(Anhedonia):** Question numbers 8, 10
- Appetite:** Question numbers 1, 18
- Sleep:** Question numbers 5, 11, 19
- Thinking / concentration:** Question numbers 3, 20
- Guilt(Worthlessness):** Question numbers 9, 17
- Tired(fatigue):** Question numbers 7, 16
- Movement(Agitation):** Question numbers 12, 13
- Suicidal ideation:** Question numbers 14, 15

Calculating the overall CESD-style symptom score. The response values for each question are:

- Not at all or less than one day = 0
- 1-2 days = 1
- 3-4 days = 2
- 5-7 days = 3
- Nearly every day for 2 weeks = 4

"The Total CESD-R Score is calculated as a sum of responses to all 20 questions. The determination of possible depressive symptom category is based upon an algorithm with the following logic:

- **Meets criteria for Major depressive episode:** Anhedonia or dysphoria nearly every day for the past two weeks, plus symptoms in an additional 4 DSM symptom groups noted as occurring nearly every day for the past two weeks;
- **Probable major depressive episode:** Anhedonia or dysphoria nearly every day for

the past two weeks, plus symptoms in an additional 3 DSM symptom groups reported as occurring either nearly every day for the past two weeks, or 5-7 days in the past week;

● **Possible major depressive episode:** Anhedonia or dysphoria nearly every day for the past two weeks, plus symptoms in an additional 2 other DSM symptom groups reported as occurring either nearly every day for the past two weeks, or 5-7 days in the past week;

● **Subthreshold depression symptoms:** People who have a CESD-style score of at least 16 but do not meet above criteria;

● **No clinical significance:** People who have a total CESD-style score less than 16 across all 20 questions.” [10]

PHQ-2 and PHQ-9

Patient Health Questionnaire-9 is a clinical tool used to assist the clinician in the diagnosis of depression, to quantify depression symptoms and to monitor the severity. [6]

“When screening for depression the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-2) can be used first (it has a 97% sensitivity and a 67% specificity) [25]. If this is positive, the PHQ-9 can then be used, which has 61% sensitivity and 94% specificity in adults [15].

Fig. 5 Patient Health Questionnaire-2 [14]

“The PHQ-9 is a multipurpose instrument for screening, monitoring, measuring the severity of depression.”[15] It was developed by Drs. R.L. Spitzer, J.B.W. Williams, K. Kroenke and

colleagues, with an educational grant from Pfizer, Inc.

Fig. 6 Patient Health Questionnaire-9 [15]

C. Feature Identification

After researching all the above standard approaches, it reveals the common features that lie under the below categories:

- Sadness(Dysphoria)
- Loss of Interest(Anhedonia)
- Appetite
- Sleep
- Thinking / concentration
- Guilt(Worthlessness)
- Tired(fatigue)

- Movement(Agitation)
- Suicidal ideation

Therefore, the above are a must-have in our survey design. In addition, I added questions to collect multi-media dataset (facial videos, language responses to mood induction questions) in order to analyze verbal and non-verbal cues using AI technologies.

There are debates on whether to consider family history of depressive episodes. Several researches have different inconsistencies or have failed to give reproducible results [16][17][18]. Therefore, we decided not to include it in our survey design.

IV. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE BASED APPROACH

A. Survey Design

We designed a unique survey to enable AI data analysis. Since our audience are adolescents and young adults who will take the survey outside of a clinical setting, we intend to make the survey age relevant and engaging.

The survey includes mood induction content intended to cause an emotional reaction. The surveyee is instructed to improvise a short video reflecting their emotional reaction to the chosen pictures. We revised this image list based on feedback from 51 US high school students. Besides video data collection, we inherit some essential survey questions from the traditional clinic questionnaire.

Tell us your candid take away from the following video on kindness
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8WiQUWLeT9I>

How often have you been feeling the following ways in the past two weeks?

	Never	Rarely	Half the time	Most times	Always
Hopeless	<input type="radio"/>				
Disinterest in doing things	<input type="radio"/>				
Feel bad about yourself(ex. feeling like you have failed)	<input type="radio"/>				
Feel like your family/friends are better off without you	<input type="radio"/>				
Had thoughts about causing harm to yourself	<input type="radio"/>				
Lost interest in things you used to enjoy	<input type="radio"/>				
Pressured	<input type="radio"/>				
Anxious	<input type="radio"/>				
Loss of sleep or appetite	<input type="radio"/>				
Seriously considered or have caused harm to yourself	<input type="radio"/>				

Fig. 7 AI based Depression Survey Form for Young Adults

Scoring design:

- Never = 0
- Rarely = 1
- Half the Time = 2
- Most Times = 3
- Always = 4

B. Facial Emotion Recognition AI Experiments

We experimented with both off-the-shelf AI APIs as well as building our own neural network models.

TABLE 1
Microsoft Azure Face API Pros and Cons
Perceived Emotion Recognition

Pros	Cons
7 Different Emotions: anger, contempt, disgust, fear, happiness, neutral, sadness, surprise	Does not give information relating to the position of a person’s facial aspects
Includes a confidence score for each emotion	
Obtaining results is relatively quick	

TABLE 2
Google Vision API Pros and Cons

Pros	Cons
4 Different Emotions: joy, sorrow, anger, and surprise	Not as many emotions as Microsoft Azure Face API
Position (bounding box) for eyes, eyebrows, nose, lips, chin, etc. (detects facial aspects)	Does not include confidence scores for each emotion
	Harder to quantify the emotion and make more informed decisions

We verified the APIs using two of the open datasets on Kaggle with 6,000+ images. Google Coud Vision API produced 33-36% accuracy rate. Microsoft Azure Face API produced a comparable accuracy rate.

One possible reason is that the image source has 48x48 pixels. Given higher image resolution, the AI APIs will produce much higher accuracy rates.

After this experiment, we decided to build our own CNN models.

Facial Expression Recognition With Convolutional Neural Network

We built multiple hidden layers in our CNN architecture using Keras with Numpy, Pandas and opencv-python libraries, and used Haarcascade to recognize facial areas for data pre-processing.

We started out with a labeled dataset containing images of people with different emotions on their face. There was a total of over 35 thousand images with seven labels in our dataset: anger, fear, disgust, happiness, sadness, surprise, and neutral.

Data Preparation

```
X_train,train_y,X_test,test_y=[],[],[],[]
for index, row in df.iterrows():
    val=row['pixels'].split(" ")
    try:
        if 'Training' in row['Usage']:
            X_train.append(np.array(val,'float32'))
            train_y.append(row['emotion'])
        elif 'PublicTest' in row['Usage']:
            X_test.append(np.array(val,'float32'))
            test_y.append(row['emotion'])
    except:
        print(f"error occured at index :{index} and row:{row}")
```

Before we trained the model, we normalized all of the data to a common scale between 0 and 1. Otherwise, different features have different ranges of values and hence gradients may end up taking a long time and can oscillate back and forth before finding its way to the global optimum.

```
X_train -= np.mean(X_train, axis=0)
X_train /= np.std(X_train, axis=0)

X_test -= np.mean(X_test, axis=0)
X_test /= np.std(X_test, axis=0)
```

```
num_features = 64
num_labels = 7
batch_size = 64
epochs = 30
width, height = 48, 48

X_train = X_train.reshape(X_train.shape[0], width, height, 1)
X_test = X_test.reshape(X_test.shape[0], width, height, 1)
```

Design CNN Model

We stacked three convolution hidden layers in order from input to output.

```
# Sequential model
model = Sequential()

# 1st Layer
model.add(Conv2D(num_features, kernel_size=(3, 3), activation='relu', input_shape=X_train.shape[1:]))
model.add(Conv2D(num_features, kernel_size=(3, 3), activation='relu'))
model.add(MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2,2), strides=(2, 2)))
model.add(Dropout(0.5))
```

```
#2nd convolution layer
model.add(Conv2D(64, (3, 3), activation='relu'))
model.add(Conv2D(64, (3, 3), activation='relu'))
model.add(MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2,2), strides=(2, 2)))
model.add(Dropout(0.5))

#3rd convolution layer
# double the number of features
model.add(Conv2D(128, (3, 3), activation='relu'))
model.add(Conv2D(128, (3, 3), activation='relu'))
model.add(MaxPooling2D(pool_size=(2,2), strides=(2, 2)))
```

The kernel size for each of our convolutions was 3 by 3, and we used the rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation function. After each convolution layer, we performed the Max Pooling function to reduce the dimension sizes and decrease the computational power. Max Pooling replaces a 3x3 area with a single data value: the greatest value in the grid. CNN also utilizes local spatial cohesion to identify groups of pixels with the most importance. E.g. if a number is written on a white background, the CNN is able to recognize that the darker pixels are where the number is instead of examining the whole image. This mitigates the risk of shift in the image. An additional benefit of using pooling layers is that it also prevents model overfitting.

Also, we added a Dropout function to avoid overfitting.

Towards the end of the architecture, we used Flatten function to linearize the neurons and used Dense() layer in Keras to enter our fully connected layer.

```
model.add(Flatten())

model.add(Dense(1024, activation='relu'))
model.add(Dropout(0.2))
model.add(Dense(1024, activation='relu'))
model.add(Dropout(0.2))
```

For our output layer, we decided to use the Softmax activation function so that we could categorize the images into multiple groups.

```
# Output layer
model.add(Dense(num_labels, activation='softmax'))
```

```
Model: "sequential_1"
```

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)	(None, 46, 46, 64)	640
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)	(None, 44, 44, 64)	36928
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 22, 22, 64)	0
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 22, 22, 64)	0
conv2d_3 (Conv2D)	(None, 20, 20, 64)	36928
conv2d_4 (Conv2D)	(None, 18, 18, 64)	36928
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 9, 9, 64)	0
dropout_2 (Dropout)	(None, 9, 9, 64)	0
conv2d_5 (Conv2D)	(None, 7, 7, 128)	73856
conv2d_6 (Conv2D)	(None, 5, 5, 128)	147584
max_pooling2d_3 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 2, 2, 128)	0
flatten_1 (Flatten)	(None, 512)	0
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 1024)	525312
dropout_3 (Dropout)	(None, 1024)	0
dense_2 (Dense)	(None, 1024)	1049600
dropout_4 (Dropout)	(None, 1024)	0
dense_3 (Dense)	(None, 7)	7175

```
Total params: 1,914,951
Trainable params: 1,914,951
Non-trainable params: 0
```

Fig. 8 Overview of the CNN architecture

Compile Model

Next, we used the Adam optimizer function to optimize the input weights by minimizing the cost function and adjusting the weights. We used `categorical_crossentropy` as probabilistic losses because we have 7 emotion labels, and the labels used one-hot representation.

```
#Compile the model
model.compile(loss=categorical_crossentropy,
              optimizer=Adam(),
              metrics=['accuracy'])
```

Train Model

To prevent the training iterations from performing on the same subset of training dataset and hence causing the training to be stuck on the local optimum without reaching the global optimum, we implemented batch and shuffle.

```
# Training the model
model.fit(X_train, train_y,
         batch_size=batch_size,
         epochs=epochs,
         verbose=1,
         validation_data=(X_test, test_y),
         shuffle=True)
```

Save Model

We saved the architecture of the model in json format and saved optimized weights in Hierarchical Data Format v5. This grid format is ideal for storing multi-dimensional arrays of numbers.

```
# Save the model to use later
fer_json = model.to_json()

with open("fer.json", "w") as json_file:
    json_file.write(fer_json)
model.save_weights("fer.h5")
```

Client Side Emotional Recognition

We used haarcascade frontal face detection to first process the image and identify the facial area, and then applied our trained models for emotion recognition. Cv2 library was used for video processing and image annotation.

Here is the core of the client code:

```
while True:
    ret, test_img = cap.read()
    if not ret:
        continue

    gray_img = cv2.cvtColor(test_img, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)

    faces_detected = face_haar_cascade.detectMultiScale(gray_img, 1.32, 5)

    for (x, y, w, h) in faces_detected:
        cv2.rectangle(test_img, (x, y), (x+w, y+h), (255, 0, 0), thickness=7)
        roi_gray = gray_img[y:y+h, x:x+w]
        roi_gray = cv2.resize(roi_gray, (48, 48))
        img_pixels = image.img_to_array(roi_gray)
        img_pixels = np.expand_dims(img_pixels, axis=0)
        img_pixels /= 255

        predictions = model.predict(img_pixels)

        #find max indexed array
        max_index = np.argmax(predictions[0])

        emotions = ('angry', 'disgust', 'fear', 'happy', 'sad', 'surprise', 'neutral')
        predicted_emotion = emotions[max_index]

        cv2.putText(test_img, predicted_emotion, (int(x), int(y)), cv2.FONT_HERSHEY_SIMPLEX, 1, (0, 0, 255), 2)

    resized_img = cv2.resize(test_img, (1000, 700))
    cv2.imshow('Facial emotion analysis', resized_img)
```

After varying the hyper-parameters and the number of epochs, we discovered the model peaked at around 80 epochs. The model yielded around 83% accuracy.

C. Natural Language Emotion Analysis With Machine Learning

Machine Learning algorithms can not work with raw text content. They will have to be converted to numbers in vectors form. We used both Bag-of-Word and TF-IDF for text vectorization and feature extraction. These two approaches greatly improve the performance compared to the basic word counts.

A Bag-of-Word(BoW) model represents the occurrence of words within a document: a vocabulary of known words and a measure of the counts of known words. The assumption here is that the documents are similar if they have similar content.

Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) is a statistical measure that evaluates how relevant a word is to a document in a collection of documents. This measure increases proportionally to the number of times a word appears in a document, but is offset by the number of documents that contain this word. So the common words across all documents rank low, e.g. this, and, what.

The simplest way to calculate the term frequency (TF) is the count of a word in a document.

The inverse document frequency (IDF) is calculated by the logarithm of (total number of documents/the number of documents containing the word). So the more common the word across documents, the result is closer to 0.

TF-IDF score is the multiplication of TF and IDF.

Bag-of-Word Train & Predict Models

Extract features with Bag-of-Words

```
[ ] from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import CountVectorizer, TfidfVectorizer

cv = CountVectorizer(stop_words=stop_words,max_features=10000)
cv_train_features = cv.fit_transform(phrase_train)
```

Build logistic regression model and setup training and prediction process

```
[ ] from sklearn import metrics
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder
from sklearn.base import clone
from sklearn.preprocessing import label_binarize
from scipy import interp
from sklearn.metrics import roc_curve, auc

def train_predict_model(classifier,
                        train_features, train_labels,
                        test_features, test_labels):

    # build model
    classifier.fit(train_features, train_labels)
    # predict using model
    predictions = classifier.predict(test_features)
    return predictions
```

```
[ ] from sklearn.linear_model import SGDClassifier, LogisticRegression

lr = LogisticRegression(penalty='l2', max_iter=100, C=1)
```

```
[ ] lr_bow_predictions = train_predict_model(classifier=lr,
                                           train_features=cv_train_features, train_labels=sentiments_train,
                                           test_features=cv_test_features, test_labels=sentiments_test)

# print(phrase)
print(sentiments_train)
```

Output results

```
[ ] df1 = pd.DataFrame(data=phrase_test, columns=["Text"])

df2 = pd.DataFrame(data=lr_bow_predictions, columns=["Result"])

def get_label2(row):
    if(row['Result'] == 1):
        return "False"
    else:
        return "True"

df2['Result'] = df2.apply(lambda row: get_label2(row), axis=1)

result = pd.concat([df1, df2], axis=1)
result
```

	Text	Result
0	"RT @dollasigndoryyy: Ppl dont fake depression...	True
1	"RT @BrandiAlexandir: Sex educators from the h...	False
2	"RT @dollasigndoryyy: Ppl dont fake depression...	True
3	"RT @dollasigndoryyy: Ppl dont fake depression...	True
4	"RT @dollasigndoryyy: Ppl dont fake depression...	True
...
4352	"RT @NPR: Surveys are finding more depression ...	False
4353	"& it was at those moments that I knew I s...	False
4354	"RT @dollasigndoryyy: Ppl dont fake depression...	True
4355	"RT @dollasigndoryyy: Ppl dont fake depression...	True
4356	"RT @dollasigndoryyy: Ppl dont fake depression...	True

4357 rows × 2 columns

Extract Features With TF-IDF

```
[ ] tv = TfidfVectorizer(min_df=0.0, max_df=1.0, ngram_range=(1,2),
                        sublinear_tf=True)
tv_train_features = tv.fit_transform(phrase_train)

[ ] lr_tfidf_predictions = train_predict_model(classifier=lr,
                                             train_features=tv_train_features, train_labels=sentiments_train,
                                             test_features=tv_test_features, test_labels=sentiments_test)
```

Output results

```
[ ] df1 = pd.DataFrame(data=phrase_test, columns=["Text"])

df2 = pd.DataFrame(data=lr_tfidf_predictions, columns=["Result"])

def get_label2(row):
    if(row['Result'] == 1):
        return "False"
    else:
        return "True"
df2['Result'] = df2.apply(lambda row: get_label2(row), axis=1)

result = pd.concat([df1, df2], axis=1)
result
```

	Text	Result
0	"RT @dollasignordoryyy: Ppl dont fake depression...	True
1	"RT @BrandiAlexandir: Sex educators from the h...	False
2	"RT @dollasignordoryyy: Ppl dont fake depression...	True
3	"RT @dollasignordoryyy: Ppl dont fake depression...	True
4	"RT @dollasignordoryyy: Ppl dont fake depression...	True
...
4352	"RT @NPR: Surveys are finding more depression ...	False
4353	"& it was at those moments that I knew I s...	False
4354	"RT @dollasignordoryyy: Ppl dont fake depression...	True
4355	"RT @dollasignordoryyy: Ppl dont fake depression...	True
4356	"RT @dollasignordoryyy: Ppl dont fake depression...	True

4357 rows x 2 columns

The accuracy was averaged at 84% for natural language emotional recognition analysis.

D. Social Media Content Analysis

Binary logistic regression analysis revealed that youth who reported higher depression symptoms were two times more likely to disclose negative emotions online and were three times more likely to disclose various hassles online than their peers who reported lower symptoms. [19]

We leveraged the massive social media data for depression sentiment analysis. We crawled,

tokenized, and labeled the tweets using Twitter Search Engine Filtered/Streaming API (<https://developer.twitter.com/en/portal/products>) and set the keyword: “Depression,” “Depressed,” “Stressed.” We collected tweets in November, 2020 for data assessment.

Here are the key Python functions.

```
22 def sentence_analysis(response_line):
23     with open(file_name, 'a') as csvfile:
24         csv_writer = csv.DictWriter(
25             f=csvfile,
26             fieldnames=["text", "author_id", "conversation_id", "created_at", "geo", "lang", "
27                 "possibly_sensitive", "source", "Timestamp", "Sentiment", "Score"]
28         )
29         data = json.loads(response_line)["data"]
30
31         print(data)
32         try:
33             text = data["text"]
34         except KeyError as ke:
35             text = ""
36
37         try:
38             author_id = data["author_id"]
39         except KeyError as ke:
40             author_id = ""
41
42         try:
43             conversation_id = data["conversation_id"]
44         except KeyError as ke:
45             conversation_id = ""
46
47         try:
48             created_at = data["created_at"]
49         except KeyError as ke:
50             created_at = ""
51
52         try:
53             geo = data["geo"]
```

```
101 sid=Vader()
102 ss=sid.polarity_scores(text)
103
104 if ss['pos']>0 and ss['compound']>0:
105     sentimentalStatus='Positive'
106 elif ss['neg']>0 and ss['compound']<0:
107     sentimentalStatus='Negative'
108 else:
109     sentimentalStatus='neutral'
110
111 csv_writer.writerow({
112     'text': "\n"+text.replace("\n", "").replace(",","")+ "\n",
113     'author_id': author_id,
114     'conversation_id': conversation_id,
115     'created_at': created_at,
116     'geo': geo,
117     'lang': lang,
118     'like_count': like_count,
119     'reply_count': reply_count,
120     'retweet_count': retweet_count,
121     'possibly_sensitive': possibly_sensitive,
122     'source': source,
123     'Timestamp': time.time(),
124     'Sentiment': sentimentalStatus,
125     'Score': ss['compound']
126 })
127
128 time.sleep(1)
```

```
187 def get_stream(headers, set, bearer_token):
188     response = requests.get(
189         "https://api.twitter.com/2/tweets/search/stream?tweet.fields=author_id,conversation_
190         headers=headers, stream=True,
191     )
192     print(response.status_code)
193     if response.status_code != 200:
194         raise Exception(
195             "Cannot get stream (HTTP {}): {}".format(
196                 response.status_code, response.text
197         )
198     )
199     for response_line in response.iter_lines():
200         if response_line:
201             sentence_analysis(response_line)
```

To visualize the keywords in the collected message, we used Google colab notebook to build a wordcloud (you may see partial words, because we obfuscated some inappropriate words for our audience).

Fig. 9 Depression WordCloud Generated in Google Colab

To assist cohort analysis, we used the AgePredictor (<https://github.com/USCDataScience/AgePredictor>) library.

The above various AI experiments converged to the conclusion that AI technologies can play a big role in detecting non-verbal facial emotional cues and natural language depression signals. It can be used as an early screen outreach tool to raise awareness in young adults.

D. Words of Caution

AI can be used for early screening. But up till now, AI is not the tool to define depression. Humans have identified a list of symptoms with years of clinical experience. Even today there is not

a universally accepted definition for the term depression. A book from University of Pennsylvania says, “Although depression (or melancholia) has been recognized as a clinical syndrome for over 2,000 years, as yet no completely satisfactory explanation of its puzzling and paradoxical features has been found.”

Also, AI is not meant to replace humans in the depression detection process and instead help them. AI enabled tools and PHQ-9 questionnaires can usefully detect symptoms. It is important that clinicians also assess contextual factors and general functioning, and do not solely rely on the tools [20]. By nature, the result of AI largely depends on the representativeness and scale of the training dataset. AI is based on statistical analysis and has a certain confidence score associated with each result.

V. NEXT STEPS

A. Longitudinal Data Analysis

Fig. 10 Longitudinal vs Cross-sectional [21]

A Longitudinal Study (longitudinal survey or panel study) data research technique involves the repeated observation of the same sample audience group over short or long periods of time [22], whereas Cross-Sectional studies takes observations of different populations in one point of time.

Longitudinal Study is an observational one and it is often applied in human psychology to understand societal and human behaviors, and come up with predictors of some human nature problems such as diseases or mental disorders.

For example, in the study conducted by Drs Fergurson and Woodward [23], they selected a cohort of 1265 children during a longitudinal 21-year period to find the correlation between age range and the likelihood of developing greater disorders or dysfunctions when young people develop depression in their mid-adolescence. The results showed a direct linkage between early depression and further development of anxiety, substance dependency and other outcomes.

There are two types of cohort-based longitudinal studies:

- Retrospective, where you collect past data from sources. They are usually cheaper and based on repositories
- Prospective, where you collect data on real time by using digital tools

In order to define the characteristics of the data to be analyzed, we need to design a number of cohorts and their features.

TABLE-3
Cohorts Design

Ethnicity	Size	Period	Ages	Family Household Income
Asian	1,000	14 years	15-29	>100K

Asian	1,000	14 years	15-29	50K - 100K
Latino	1,000	14 years	15-29	>100K
Latino	1,000	14 years		50K - 100K
...				

B. Intervention Strategies

Now we can reveal the depression symptoms earlier. The ultimate goal is to prevent the symptoms from further progressing. As part of the next steps, we need to develop software tools to improve mental health including taking suitable amounts of daily physical activities, sleeping well, eating a healthy diet, and reaching out to family and friends, especially in times of crisis and pandemic. We are in a quest for this mission.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Based on our studies on the current major self report and clinical screening tools (CES-D, CESD-R, PHQ-2 and PHQ-9), and our AI experiments on facial emotional expression cues, natural language contextual analysis, and young adults social media data sentiment analysis, we concluded that there is a large correlation between emotional signals discovered by AI tools and depression symptoms. Therefore, AI tools can play a big role in detecting emotional

symptoms of depression before they progress to neurovegetative and neurocognitive symptoms. AI can be used as an early screen outreach tool to raise awareness in young adults and reveal complementary cues to assist clinical depression detections.

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